

As an NIH-funded researcher, I want to USE Dryad to share my data, so that I can comply with my data management and sharing plan and the conditions of my grant.

This use case highlights ways research teams can leverage generalist repositories to share project data.

Dataset title:

Deep evolutionary analysis reveals the design principles of fold A glycosyltransferases
<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.v15dv41sh>

Investigators and affiliations:

Taujale, Rahil et al.

Publication date:

April 10, 2020

Data type:

FASTA and TSV

Citations:

Rahil Taujale, et al. (2020). "Deep evolutionary analysis reveals the design principles of fold A glycosyltransferases," *eLife*
<https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.54532>

Use case date:

April 2023

Use case contact:

hello@datadryad.org

Background:

As an NIH-funded researcher, I am required to submit my data to an approved repository. I have FASTA and TSV files containing GT-A fold sequences and have determined that a suitable domain-specific repository does not exist. I have confirmed that the data is shareable under a CC0 license and does not contain any sensitive or personally identifying information. I want to ensure that my dataset is discoverable, citable, and connected to the research article it underlies.

Process:

I login to datadryad.org using my ORCID iD and check to see if my institution is a Dryad member (https://datadryad.org/stash/join_us#members). I complete Dryad's straightforward submission process, which collects metadata necessary for discovery and reuse. I indicate NIH as a granting organization and enter my grant number. I upload my data files and a detailed README describing my methods, the file structure and contents of my submission, variable definitions, and other information necessary for reuse. Through Dryad's integration with Zenodo, I also seamlessly upload code needed to replicate my analyses. I receive a DOI upon submission.

Within a few days, a Dryad curator will confirm whether my data are appropriate for open sharing, follow FAIR principles, and meet ethical standards for publication. They will also offer guidance on best practices for creating reusable data and help me navigate publication requirements. They will not attempt to assess the rigor of my methods or validate my findings.

My data will be published openly via datadryad.org.

Login	Submit	Review	Cite
Use your ORCID. If your institution is a Dryad member , connect to your existing credentials.	Upload your data files and receive a citable DOI.	Our curators will thoroughly check your submission to ensure the data are appropriate and ready for sharing and reuse. They may contact you with advice or questions.	Cite and promote your data publication.

GREI Use Cases are supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Data Science Strategy/ Office of the NIH Director pursuant to OTA-21-009, "Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)". NIH Image Gallery. GDF10 protein forms new brain cell connections (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/nihgov/22798807131/>). Courtesy of S. Thomas Carmichael, MD, PhD, David Geffen School of Medicine at the University of California Los Angeles. NIH funding: National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS). More information at <https://www.nih.gov/news-events/news-releases/scientists-identify-main-component-brain-repair-after-stroke>

As a researcher, I want to **FIND** research data of interest in Dryad so that I can validate findings, reuse data, and build on work within my discipline.

This use case highlights ways researchers can leverage Dryad to find datasets for reuse.

Dataset title:

Deep evolutionary analysis reveals the design principles of fold A glycosyltransferases
<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.v15dv41sh>

Investigators and affiliations:

Taujale, Rahil et al.

Publication date:

April 10, 2020

Data type:

FASTA and TSV

Citations:

Rahil Taujale, et al. (2020). "Deep evolutionary analysis reveals the design principles of fold A glycosyltransferases," *eLife*
<https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.54532>

Use case date:

May 2023

Use case contact:

hello@datadryad.org

Background:

I am a doctoral student interested in the application of glycosyltransferases for drug development. I am looking for data to use in a meta-analysis as part of my dissertation research.

Use case:

Finding data for reuse can take many different forms. All data in Dryad are licensed under the Creative Commons Public Domain License Waiver (also known as CC0). That means that all of our datasets are free to access and to reuse without restriction.

1. **Use Dryad's search interface.** Enter your keywords (e.g., "glycotransferase") at <https://datadryad.org/search>. Refine results by subject, geography, journal, institutional affiliation of the authors, file extensions, and funders.
2. **Use Dryad's browse features.** Browse by place name, subject, journal, or institution at <https://datadryad.org/search>.
3. **Use Dryad's open API.** Search for keywords (e.g., "glycotransferase") using our open API. Learn how at <https://datadryad.org/api/v2/docs/>.
4. **Search aggregators and indexes.** You can find Dryad data in DataCite Commons, Google Dataset Search, Google, Web of Science, Scopus, and more.
5. **Check data availability statements in our partner publications.** Dryad integrates with dozens of journals, making it simple for authors to deposit data when they submit a manuscript. You can find Dryad datasets connected to publications in over 1200 academic journals.

As an institution, I want to **REPORT** on all datasets from my institution in Dryad, so that I can ensure compliance of research data sharing and management plan commitments by our researchers.

This use case highlights ways administrators can leverage Dryad to track and report data sharing at an organizational level.

Use case date:

May 2023

Use case contact:

hello@datadryad.org

Use case:

The University New Mexico (UNM) is a research intensive public university with distinct strengths in engineering and physics. UNM has been a Dryad member since 2019, but their researchers deposit data in a wide range of specialist repositories as well as an institutional data repository. To understand the full scope of the institution's data output and to archive an additional preservation copy of their researchers' data, UNM systematically harvests Dryad data through an integration with our open API.

As one of the first integrators of Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifiers, Dryad provides a simple and reliable way to identify datasets affiliated with a range of research organizations, including universities, institutes, and societies. By querying our API with their ROR ID as a parameter, UNM can reliably harvest all Dryad data and metadata associated with a UNM researcher. To learn more about the API and try it out for yourself, visit <https://datadryad.org/api/v2/docs/>.

As a Dryad institutional member, UNM also has access to an interactive administrative dashboard, where they can find metadata, usage metrics, and more information about all datasets for their affiliated researchers. They can download all of the information in tabular format (.csv file) for ingest into research tracking systems or data analysis and visualization programs.

Admin Dashboard

At a glance: 82,796 Users, 71,005 Datasets

Activity in the last 7 days: 244 users added, 209 datasets started, 128 datasets submitted

dryad-api 2.1.0 OAS3
[/openapi.yml](https://openapi.yml)

Title	Status	Author	DOI	Last Modified	Curator	Size	Date
Why flowers close at noon? A case study of an alpine species <i>Gentianopsis paludosa</i> (Gentianaceae)	Curation	Duan; Ehmet; Hou; Pang; Shao; Sun; Zhao	10.5061/dryad.qy9s4mwwg4	03/08/2022 11:31:06 UTC	Jessica Herzog	615.30 KB	January 15, 2022
CV and colony data vesnid mandible wear	Curation	Lagos-Oviedo; Sarmiento	10.5061/dryad.fbg79cck	03/13/2022 23:32:04 UTC	Jessica Herzog	293.48 KB	Not available
Seismic Data Imaging the Earth's PmPWorld	Curation	Yang	10.25349/D9QK7K	03/21/2022 16:52:05 UTC	Ryan Horne	12.45 MB	Not available

Dryad's administrative dashboard (pictured in screenshot) provides our institutional members with detailed information about datasets published by their affiliated researchers. Our API, open to all users, provides direct access to all Dryad data and metadata for querying and harvesting.

GREI Use Cases are supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Data Science Strategy/ Office of the NIH Director pursuant to OTA-21-009, "Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)". NIH Image Gallery. Mouse Retina. (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/nihgov/29820716833/>). Credit: Kenyoung Kim, Wonkyu Ju and Mark Ellisman, National Center for Microscopy and Imaging Research, University of California, San Diego. NIH support: National Institute of General Medical Sciences (NIGMS).

As a funder from a specific NIH institute or in general, I want to find datasets we have funded in Dryad, so that I can **REPORT** on compliance with policies, and **TRACK** impact of research funding and usage of data.

This use case highlights ways funders can leverage generalist repositories to track compliance with data sharing policies and understand data reuse.

Use case date:

May 2023

Use case contact:

hello@datadryad.org

Background:

As a funding body, I want to track compliance with my open data sharing policy and understand more about how and where researchers receiving funding are sharing their data.

Use Case:

Dryad integrates with Crossref’s Funder Registry to provide standardized, machine-readable funding information about the datasets we publish.

Funders can easily identify the data they sponsor by executing a blank search at <https://datadryad.org/search> (visit the link and click the magnifying glass icon without entering a search term) and then filtering by “Funder”.

Dryad members, including funders, can also gain access to our interactive administrative dashboard, which offers detailed information about datasets affiliated with the organization, including dataset metadata and usage metrics.

Funder	Count
National Institutes of Health	1,077
National Science Foundation	275
National Institute of General Medical Sciences	125

Screenshot of the “Funder” filter in Dryad’s search interface, which allows easy identification of datasets funded by a wide range of organizations.

As an **institution**, I want to **capture and preserve research data** from my institution by using multiple repositories/services, including **Dryad**, so that I can offer researchers at my institution **choices** that best fit their workflows, **meet funder requirements**, and allow my institution to get a **full picture of research output**.

This use case highlights ways generalist repositories support data sharing via institutional repository infrastructure and workflows

Use case date:

May 2024

Use case contact:

hello@datadryad.org

Use case statement:

My institution wants to provide support for researchers in aligning their data deposits with FAIR principles and data sharing best practices. We value metadata and file review by human curators is important help our researchers comply with data sharing requirements and to make it easier for future researchers to find and reuse deposited data. We want to be able to measure, track, report, and aggregate the institution's full portfolio of research outputs, including research data. We value open, non-profit, community-driven infrastructure and prefer open source options.

Background:

Dryad makes it easy for my institution to **track and harvest** our researchers' datasets. Dryad affiliates all data depositors with their institution through Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifiers so we can easily identify all of our researchers' deposits. They provide an administrative **dashboard** with one-stop access to information about data deposits, including engagement analytics (views, downloads, and citations) and maintain an **open API** that makes it easy to harvest metadata and/or data files into local repository and other systems. Dryad's platform is **turnkey** data sharing solution that does not require local technology resources. Dryad accepts data types in any format and links data to other research outputs (code, supplementary materials, data management plans, articles, preprints).

- 1) Researchers submit data to Dryad and optionally send software and supplemental information to Zenodo.
- 2) Dryad curators review metadata and files to support FAIR data practices.
- 3) Dryad openly publishes data under a CC0 license, which ensures FAIR reuse for all content, and archives it indefinitely.
- 4) Dryad makes metadata and data available via open API for simple harvesting.
- 5) Institutions harvest metadata and data files into local systems for tracking and reporting.

As of July 2021, Canada's Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR) began indexing datasets from the Dryad data repository that have an author affiliated with a Canadian institution, making these records discoverable through FRDR. This is the first time in FRDR's development history that it will pull Canadian records from an international repository ([source](#)). The initiative is made possible through Dryad's open API and standards-compliant metadata, which allows FRDR to harvest metadata and data files with ease.

Login	Submit	Review	Cite
Use your ORCID. If your institution is a Dryad member , connect to your existing credentials.	Upload your data files and receive a citable DOI.	Our curators will thoroughly check your submission to ensure the data are appropriate and ready for sharing and reuse. They may contact you with advice or questions.	Cite and promote your data publication.

As a researcher, I want to use Dryad to share Big Data, as the volume and variety of my data require specialized infrastructure and handling.

This use case highlights how Dryad supports Big Data through custom curation of large, complex datasets, supporting all file types and offering high upload limits to ensure efficient handling of diverse data.

Dataset title:

Human intestine processed CODEX multiplexed images for donors B004-6, B008 (Part 1/2)

Investigators and affiliations:

John Hickey,
Stanford University

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.76hdr7t1p>

Data type:

Large data package, many files in multiple formats

Use case date:

February 2025

Use case contact:

hello@datadryad.org

Background:

As an **NIH-funded researcher**, I want to use **Dryad** to share, curate, and preserve my large, interdisciplinary data in compliance with my data management and sharing plan (DMSP) and grant conditions. This will ensure that my data is publicly and globally accessible, easily reusable, and stored in a platform used by a broader audience, regardless of their specific area of research.

Process:

My data package is **219 GB** in size and contains dozens of files in 8 separate .zip files between 19GB and 33GB. I plan to share the dataset publicly for others to access, analyze, and build upon. However, due to its size and complexity, I need to ensure it is well-organized, properly formatted, and safe to share.

I decided to submit my large dataset to Dryad because they accept data from all research fields, offer comprehensive curation services, accept all open file types, and allow direct upload of data packages up to 300GB through their platform, or larger with direct support.

An experienced curator carefully evaluates my submission to verify accessibility, organization, clarity, and completeness in line with [Dryad's guidelines](#) and [FAIR principles](#). They suggest improvements to the file organization and offer specific guidance on improving my README file. This ensures clear, well-documented metadata, logical organization, and thorough descriptions, making the dataset easier for future users to interpret and analyze—thus enhancing its usability. It's helpful to be able to engage directly with a human curator who can answer my questions and offer swift, knowledgeable support.

When my submission is approved for publication, my dataset is immediately made publicly available and the DOI active. Future users can select specific files for download, minimizing long download times and reducing the strain on computer or machine capabilities. I can also include links to my related research article and DMSP, and track usage metrics directly from the dataset's landing page.

GREI Use Cases are supported by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Office of Data Science Strategy/ Office of the NIH Director pursuant to OTA-21-009, "Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)". NIH Image Gallery. GDF10 protein forms new brain cell connections (<https://www.flickr.com/photos/nihgov/22798807131/>). Courtesy of S. Thomas Carmichael, MD, PhD, David Geffen School of Medicine at the University of California Los Angeles. NIH funding: National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke (NINDS). More information at <https://www.nih.gov/news-events/news-releases/scientists-identify-main-component-brain-repair-after-stroke>

Exploring data sharing practices through Dryad: A researcher's insight

"Data sharing becomes extremely important for **multi-institution collaborations**, as well as **training activities** we have with scholars from other laboratories who spend time here — especially international trainees". — Troy D. Wood

Researcher: Troy D. Wood, PhD
Department of Chemistry, University at Buffalo, New York
Wood Lab: <https://woodgroupms.wixsite.com/twood>

Title: Chemical informatics combined with Kendrick mass analysis to enhance annotation and identify pathways in soybean metabolomics

Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.np5hqco46>

Supplemental information: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14536111>

Related publication: <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo15020073>

Funding: National Institutes of Health: S10-RR029517, NCRR; United Soybean Board; New York Corn & Soybean Growers Association

The screenshot shows the Dryad dataset page. At the top, it displays the title and authors: Wood, Troy¹; Tiede, Erin¹; Izydorczak, Alexandra²; Zemitis, Kevin³; Ye, Heng⁴; Nguyen, Henry⁴. The dataset is published on Jan 28, 2025. The 'Data files' section lists three files: 'Jan 28, 2025 version files' (495.64 MB), 'README.md' (3.76 KB), and 'Soybean_Metabolomics_RAW_Data.zip' (495.64 MB). The 'Abstract' section describes the study: 'Among abiotic stresses to agricultural crops, drought stress is the most prolific and has worldwide detrimental impacts. The soybean (*Glycine max*) is one of the most important sources of nutrition to both livestock and humans. Different plant introductions (PI) of soybeans have been identified to have different drought tolerance levels. Here, two soybean lines, Pana (drought sensitive) and PI 567731 (drought tolerant) were selected to identify chemical compounds and pathways which could be targets for metabolomic analysis induced by abiotic stress. Extracts from the two lines are analyzed by direct infusion electrospray ionization Fourier transform ion cyclotron resonance mass spectrometry. The high mass resolution and accuracy of the method allows for identification of ions from hundreds of different compounds in each cultivar. The exact *m/z* of these species were filtered through SoyCyc and the Human Metabolome Database to identify possible molecular formulas of the ions. Next, the exact *m/z* values are converted into Kendrick masses and their Kendrick mass defects (KMD) computed, which are then sorted from high to low KMD. This latter process assists in identifying many additional molecular formulas, and is noted to be particularly useful in identifying formulas whose mass difference corresponds to two hydrogen atoms. In this study, more than 460 ionic formulas are identified in Pana, and more than 340 ionic formulas are identified in PI 567731, with many of these formulas reported from soybean for the first time. Using the SoyCyc matches, the metabolic pathways from each cultivar are compared, providing for lists of molecular targets available to profile effects of abiotic

Dataset overview and analytical application

This dataset is valuable to researchers exploring the **metabolomics** and **metabolic pathways** of soybean plants, particularly those designing or analyzing plant phenotypes for adaptation to environmental stressors.

Additionally, the dataset serves as a useful reference for practitioners of mass spectrometry. It provides a practical example of applying the **Kendrick Mass Defect (KMD) principle** to complex biological specimens — highlighting its utility in metabolomic studies and distinguishing it from more traditional applications in petroleomics.

Keywords: Kendrick mass defect; metabolomics; soybean; electrospray ionization; drought; FT-ICR; chemical informatics

Evolving practices in data sharing

Data sharing has seen significant evolution in the last decade according to Dr. Wood. In the past, metabolomics researchers would share mass spectrometry data only upon receiving a written request. Today, researchers can openly share data, including large data, using public repositories.

This shift has had a meaningful impact on the field. One of the most significant outcomes is the ability to mine publicly available datasets to identify common metabolites, which can help validate findings or refine hypotheses about biological pathways and metabolics. Dr. Wood noted that this change “should accelerate all kinds of discovery aspects in metabolomics.”

Choosing a data repository

Dr. Wood chose to explore a generalist repository for this dataset because the project involved collaborators from another institution. Additionally, the journal required the data to be publicly available in an open-access format. He mentioned, “Given these factors, and my previous positive experience, Dryad was the clear choice.”

Why Dryad?

According to Dr. Wood, one of Dryad's most valuable features is its experienced curation team—real people who provide hands-on support for every dataset to ensure quality, consistency, and usability. For this dataset specifically, a Dryad data curator identified a missing data folder (“a great quality control step”) and also offered an “excellent suggestion” to expand the user instructions to improve accessibility which is especially important for those unfamiliar with the specific instrument data formats used.

These suggestions were incorporated into the final submission and ultimately enhanced the dataset's clarity and usability for the broader research community, said Wood.

Enabling discovery through data sharing

Dr. Wood emphasized that open data sharing has transformed the landscape of plant metabolomics. Platforms like Dryad, coupled with field-wide standards and community-driven best practices, are accelerating discovery and making collaboration across labs and borders far more effective. Dr. Wood explained that data sharing “has simplified working with researchers from other institutions, especially trainees from overseas who spend weeks or months in the lab acquiring data locally, but will need access to the data subsequent to their return to their home institutions. I can see us using this more extensively in the near-term.”

By sharing this dataset, Dr. Wood hopes to support ongoing work in plant stress biology and metabolomics, while encouraging others in the field to adopt open data practices for the benefit of the wider scientific community.

Dr. Wood's tips for researchers considering open data sharing:

- **Use open formats** to ensure accessibility across platforms and collaborators.
- **Select repositories** that offer robust curation and dedicated submission support.
- **Plan for long-term access**, especially for international or temporary collaborators.
- **Provide clear usage instructions** to help users navigate data formats and avoid common accessibility issues.

Data sharing with Dryad: Finding the right home for human research data

"As a researcher, I'm a proponent of transparency and rigor because it's how others can duplicate our work, validate our work, or build upon it. So I think that it's a very good thing that we share our data."

— Ann Van de Winckel

Researcher: Ann Van de Winckel, PhD, MSPT, PT
Tenured Associate Professor in the Division of Physical Therapy and Rehabilitation Medicine at the UMN Medical School, and Director of the Brain Body Mind Lab
<https://med.umn.edu/familymedicine/research/programs-centers/rehabilitation-science/labs/brain-body-mind-lab>

Title: Finding functionality: Rasch analysis of the Functionality Appreciation Scale in community-dwelling adults in the US

Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.66t1g1k4d>

Related publication: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fresc.2023.1222892>

Funding: National Institutes of Health's National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences

The screenshot shows the Dryad dataset page. At the top, it displays the title and authors: Feng, Sarah; McDaniel, Sydney; and Van de Winckel, Ann. It includes author affiliations and the research facility: Division of Physical Therapy, Department of Rehabilitation Medicine, Medical School, University of Minnesota. The publication date is Nov 03, 2023, and the update date is Nov 12, 2023. The DOI is <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.66t1g1k4d>.

The 'Data files' section lists several files:

File Name	Size
Nov 03, 2023 version files	63.79 KB
Nov 12, 2023 version files	122.93 KB
Consent_and_capacity_to_consent.pdf	65.76 KB
FAS_data_10.30.2023_for_DRYAD.xlsx	52.49 KB
README.md	4.68 KB

The 'Abstract' section includes an introduction, methods, results, and discussion. The introduction states that the Functionality Appreciation Scale (FAS) measures an individual's appreciation for their functions. The methods describe the recruitment of 567 participants at the Minnesota State Fair. The results show that the FAS had good person and item fit, and the PCAR and subsequent paired t-tests confirmed the unidimensionality of the scale. The discussion notes that the 6-item Rasch-based FAS demonstrated unidimensionality and good item fit, but more difficult items need to be added for better reliability.

Dataset overview and analytical application

This study evaluated the structural validity of the **Functionality Appreciation Scale (FAS)** using **Rasch analysis** in 567 community-dwelling adults.

The findings support the structural validity of the FAS for community-dwelling adult populations while highlighting the need to introduce more challenging items to improve targeting. In addition, measurement precision needs to be improved.

Keywords: spinal cord injury; medical and health sciences; appreciation; body awareness; body image; functionality; healthy adults; validation studies

Evolving practices in data sharing

Dr. Van de Winckel noted that data sharing has changed significantly over the past decade largely due to mandates requiring it. She emphasized that increased transparency has strengthened the rigor of research by allowing others to evaluate, reproduce, and validate findings. Dr. Van de Winckel highlighted that this is important for all research fields and that there is a need to replication and validation of findings.

The availability of data repositories now ensures that methods and results are more thoroughly documented than they were 20 years ago, enhancing accountability and reproducibility.

Choosing a data repository

Initially, Dr. Van de Winckel planned to deposit her data in the University of Minnesota's DRUM repository, but she was unable to do so due to restrictions on uploading patient data. As a result, she searched for an alternative and began using Dryad prior to receiving her NIH grant.

Why Dryad?

Dr. Van de Winckel later learned that Dryad was among the repositories recommended by the National Institutes of Health as a preferred option for the National Center for Complementary and Integrative Health (NCCIH). With her university also covering data publishing fees for researchers, choosing Dryad was an easy decision.

She described being extremely pleased with the curation process, emphasizing the thorough review of her data submission and the clear, detailed guidance on what needed to be revised and how to revise it.

Dr. Van de Winckel noted that curation support was especially valuable for first-timers, since, as she put it, you can do your best but "you don't

know what you don't know." Dr. Van de Winckel also appreciated the quick turnaround time by the curators and emphasized that the team was consistently responsive and easy to communicate with.

The more you know

The very first time Dr. Van de Winckel submitted data, she was not familiar with the required README file. Because of that, there were certain elements she had not planned for in advance. Dr. Van de Winckel worked to ensure the README for her dataset was clear and easy to understand for anyone not directly involved in the data collection or with study participants.

Dr. Van de Winckel also noted that, as a first-time submitter, entering the metadata and uploading the data files required more time than expected, and additional effort was needed to ensure the data package was accurate and complete.

Key tips Dr. Van de Winckel offers for sharing data effectively, especially in human research:

1. Provide enough context for reuse. Include sufficient detail so others can actually understand and use the data—not just view it.
2. Provide detailed documentation and guidance for interpretation. For example, give the scoring range of scales and indicate whether higher scores mean better or worse outcomes.
3. Think beyond your own expertise. Prepare the dataset so that researchers who are not in your specific field can still understand and build on your work.

Overall, make data as transparent, interpretable, and user-friendly as possible to maximize its value for others.